

research digest

*An annual magazine publication of
Unida Christian Colleges
Research Department*

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS:

*Our Future,
Our Action*

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About Us

THE DEPARTMENT

Research plays a vital role in attaining innovation and excellence in the arts, science, language, mathematics, and humanities.

As Unida Christian Colleges achieves to be the most loved and admired educational institution in Imus City, the school's Research Department has become the instrument to institutionalize research, establish a research culture, and increase the research capability.

The department aims to establish a research culture where research projects are recognized and published in local, national, and international institutions, promoting social, emotional, and ethical development of the academic community.

THE MAGAZINE

Research Digest, an annual publication of Unida Christian Colleges Research Department, is a collection of the department's success stories and wins. With its goal to share knowledge, this second volume of the magazine features the events that the department conducted throughout the year including seminars, defenses, publication, the Research Trailblazers, and the 2nd Senior High School Research Colloquium.

SOCIAL MEDIA

Facebook

Youtube

Instagram

MEMBERSHIP

**International Organization of
Educators and Researchers Inc.**

The Organization

ORGANIZATIONAL CHART

Message from the Department

Dear Readers,

I am delighted to present the second volume of our research magazine, marking another milestone in our journey at Unida Christian Colleges. Established in 2021, the Research Department has quickly become a cornerstone of our institution, grounded in our department's core values of excellence, service, and integrity. This publication is a testament of hard work and passion of our students, faculty, and contributors. We extend our heartfelt gratitude to all who have brought this magazine to life, enriching our commitment to academic excellence.

Our vision, "To be one of the 'most admired' research institutions in Imus by 2026," guides all our endeavors. This magazine reflects our strides toward realizing this goal, showcasing the talent and intellectual rigor of our community. We acknowledge and appreciate the invaluable contributions of both past and present members of the research department, whose efforts have laid the foundation for our ongoing success.

We hope this magazine inspires a passion for research among our readers. As Neil deGrasse Tyson wisely said, "The good thing about science is that it's true whether or not you believe in it." This quote underscores the importance of research in education, reminding us that the pursuit of knowledge and truth is vital.

Thank you for your continued support and enthusiasm for research at Unida Christian Colleges.

Sincerely,

Mr. Raineir M. Amparo
Research Supervisor

Exploring Research...

The Research Department aimed to aid the researchers in familiarizing the quantitative research, mixed method research, and qualitative research. With this separate seminars for Grade 12 and Grade 11 students, they are able to grasp the idea of research and how to do it.

NUMBERS IN ACTION: DISCOVERING QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH

Grade 12 group representatives attended the face-to-face seminar last September 21, 2023 at the UCC Audio-Visual Center.

Mr. Lito Claveria, from Imus National High School, was the guest speaker for the STEM, ABM, and General Academic Strands.

On the other hand, Mr. Reymart Almazora, UCC Grade 12 coordinator, was the in-house speaker for the HUMSS and TVL strands.

This event inculcated the step by step process on how to conduct an effective quantitative research which is a requirement in their Practical Research 2 subject.

QUALITATIVE RESEARCH: UNDERSTANDING IMRAD STRUCTURE

Grade 11 student representatives attended the Qualitative Research Seminar last November 14 and 16, 2023 at the UCC Audio-Visual Room. The seminar introduced the structure of IMRAD Format in research.

Through the help of the in-house speakers, Ms. Keziah Medilo, Mr. Raineir Amparo, Mr. Vince Chamorro, and Mr. John Arvin Glo, this seminar helped the students in conducting their own qualitative research.

Other members of the group, both Grade 11 and 12, attended the seminar via Facebook Live.

RESEARCH QUIPS

CAN'T FIND
RRL

The RRL Conjunction

REVISE
LITERATURE
REVIEW
DAW!

The Review Anomaly

POV: REVISING
AT 2AM

more
PANCIT CANTON

The First Sleep Deprivation

Analyzing Data in Research

This seminar for senior high school students aimed to teach them on how to analyze their gathered data, both quantitative and qualitative.

BRIDGING THE GAP BETWEEN NUMBERS AND NARRATIVES IN DATA ANALYSIS

Senior High School student researchers attended the seminar titled Bridging the Gap Between Numbers and Narratives in Data Analysis, in which they learned qualitative data analysis for Grade 11, and quantitative data analysis for Grade 12.

Resource Speakers, Mr. Johndriel Vertudez and Ms. Hanny Pearl Camerino discussed how to analyze quantitative data and appropriate data analysis methods for quantitative research across all strands.

On the other hand, Guest Speaker, Mr. John Arvin Glo, discussed the process of coding and other necessary details in qualitative data analysis.

This seminar provided the students enough knowledge to conduct data analysis that can help them finish their research successfully.

A Research Validator's Journey

As a research validator for Grade 11 STEM and ABM ambassadors, my journey has been both challenging and rewarding. Working with these bright young minds from Unida Christian Colleges, became an eye-opener. They tackled diverse and intriguing topics such as factors influencing student engagement with Bing AI, perceptions of canteen food among students with health issues, and the lived experiences of residents involved in the "Basura Palit Bag Pang Skwela 2022" program in Carmona. Each study is a reflection of the students' curiosity and dedication to understanding and improving their communities.

In the beginning, most students faced significant challenges, especially when it came to ensuring that their research instruments were valid. This process required deep understanding of their topics and the ability to create surveys and interviews that accurately captured the needed data. However, the students' perseverance truly shone through. They were eager to learn, and despite the initial struggles, they continuously refined their instruments. The determination to get it right, and the desire to produce meaningful results were evident in every discussion we had.

Their hard work paid off- resulting in insightful studies that are both relevant and impactful. From exploring residents' perceptions of water sanitation practices in Sitio Santo Niño to gauging civil engineering students' interest in 3D-printing as an elective Class, these young researchers have demonstrated remarkable growth and capability. It's inspiring to see how their efforts can lead to real-world contributions, sparking ideas for future innovations and solutions.

The entire experience has been a testament to the power of perseverance and the incredible potential of our youth.

MR. BRIAN IAN BEN, LPT
Research Validator

Workshop Series in Research Writing and Publication

Research Department initiates seminars and workshops for faculty members and staff to ignite their curiosity and passion to Research. This is the second workshop series that the department has conducted.

ACTION RESEARCH ECHO SEMINAR

The Action Research Echo Seminar which was the first part of the 2nd Workshop Series for Research Writing and Publication was attended by various Ambassadors last August 2023 at the UCC Employee Lounge.

Resource Speakers, Mr. Aston Queliza and Ms. Kristine Muñoz introduced the

contents, templates, and other guidelines for Action Research to the participants.

Mr. Queliza talked about the nature of Action Research which is qualitative but stressed that it can also be quantitative.

On the other hand, Ms. Muñoz shared that action research differentiates itself from other research designs as it simultaneously conducts research and takes action.

ACTION RESEARCH ENGAGEMENT

Dr. Lydia S. Villanueva, the guest speaker, effectively talked about the process of Action Research, its cycles, and its analysis.

Dr. Villanueva also summarized Action Research into this: Find the problem, analyze the problem, and find the solution. She also emphasized that one of the purposes of Action Research is to change ineffective practices across different areas.

The seminar was then followed by a short open forum and consultation with employee researchers. Furthermore, teachers, especially in the Research Department, also gained information on how to approach student researchers during consultations, defense, and checking of manuscripts.

A Statistician's Journey

Standing at the crossroads of mathematics and research, my journey as a lead statistician has been an adventure of numbers, data, and discovery. I was thrilled when I was appointed as an in-house statistician. Even though I don't have a formal degree in statistics, I took the challenge. I have a background in Secondary Education major in Mathematics, but my love for statistics has driven me to go deeper into this field, learning and growing as I go along as a Statistics Practitioner.

Everyday is a new set of challenges and opportunities as a statistician. My tasks include providing guidance on research questions, design choices, data collection methods and statistical treatments. I also worked with other statisticians to standardize our methods and our analysis. Assisting in the preparation of research manuscripts for publication is one of the best parts of my job. Working with researchers from different fields broadens my understanding and application of statistics. Gathering feedback and evaluating the impact of our support services is important for continuous improvement. Assisting in finding relevant data sources for analysis ensures our research is data-driven.

Our involvement as statisticians does not end with data interpretation. As part of research title defenses and final defenses, we guide young researchers in making their studies feasible and statistically sound. This helps us to sharpen our critical thinking and judgment, especially when we need to interpret data for multiple research papers.

My journey as lead statistician has been transformative. It has fueled my aspiration to pursue a Master of Applied Statistics this year. I believed that this program will enable me to be recognized as a professional statistician. Not just a statistics practitioner. I want to be acknowledged in research and academia as a great statistician. Not just within my school but also outside. To achieve this, I aim to publish my own research. I know that these dreams can be fulfilled one step at a time. To those considering a career in data and statistics, I encourage you to embrace this path. The work is rewarding. It is impactful. It offers countless opportunities to learn and grow. As I continue this path, I remind myself that while I may not be the best, yet, step by step, I will achieve greatness. Keep pursuing your dreams, Ambassadors!

MS. RUBY ROSE FUNDIMERA, LPT
Statistician Lead

More Seminars for Employees...

In line with the Institutional Research Services program, the Research Department aims to equip willing teachers who wants to be statisticians and validators.

STAT UP! WORKSHOP ON STATISTICS

In collaboration with the UCC Department of Mathematics in Basic Education, the research faculty joined the Stat Up series to equip teachers in statistics which is helpful in quantitative research.

Guest Speaker, Mr. Iwyne Abenis, discussed about the non-parametric tests in statistics which is later applied to sample research using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences software.

It became a fulfilling event for research statisticians as they are equipped with knowledge and skills to help students in data analysis.

ENSURING RELIABLE ASSESSMENT: EMPOWERING TEACHERS THROUGH INSTRUMENT VALIDATION

Teachers and staff from different departments were engaged in the Instrument Validation seminar, last January 2024, at the Employees' Lounge.

This seminar is essential for both validators and student-researchers as our validators became equipped with the knowledge on what and how to validate an instrument.

Aside from the discussion proper by the keynote speaker and research teacher, Mr. Paul John Abig, the process and timeline of validation were also discussed.

It became a rich discussion as questions were answered not only by Mr. Abig, but also by other research teachers.

Instrument Validation is one of the crucial processes in data gathering for research in both quantitative and qualitative approaches.

RESEARCH QUIPS

The Distress Resonance

The Timed Breakdown

The Manuscript Materialization

Research Trailblazers

THE LOGO

The Trailblazers Logo symbolizes unity and continuity. It reinforces the idea that this department pioneers new paths and encourages students and researchers to explore uncharted discoveries, challenge conventions, and lead the way. Within the circular emblem, the laurel wreath is traditionally associated with peace and harmony. Meanwhile, the shield represents collaboration, unity, and a shared purpose.

Its green and yellow palette signifies growth, renewal, and progress that the mentees may encounter. With stars within the green quadrants representing passion and achievement, it signifies the pursuit of knowledge, and the flaming desire to shine brightly in academic endeavors. The gear found on the left side of the quadrant symbolizes technology and innovation which implies that the institution embraces modernity and adapts to changing times. While the book with laurel plant represents wisdom, and victory.

It emphasizes the institution's commitment to academic excellence, and faith-based values, inviting the students and researchers to be trailblazers, exploring, creating, and leaving a lasting impact within the research industry.

Research Trailblazers

PRESENTATIONS

Luwalhati: Food and Culture Cafe

Proponents: Francine Navarro, Ashlee Clutario, Ella Aquino, and Alliah Perico

1st Dasmariñas Research Congress

Kolehiyo ng Lungsod ng Dasmariñas

Best Paper Presenter

SUMI Travel and Tours

Proponents: Joshey Jurado, Queen Villar, Ruth Monte, and Kyle Castañeda

1st Dasmariñas Research Congress

Kolehiyo ng Lungsod ng Dasmariñas

Breaking the Tabo: A Study About Parental Acceptance of Comprehensive Sex Education in the Philippines

Proponents: Xyla Mae Brabante, Ariane Nicole Comedia, Jamie Margaret Flores, Orlando Gueta, Deanne Nicole Nati, Jan Marich Porras

Research and Innovation for Sustainable Development

4th De La Salle-Dasmariñas Senior High School Student Research Conference

Abstracts

LUWALHATI: FOOD AND CULTURE CAFE

Proponents: Francine Navarro, Ashlee Clutario, Ella Aquino, and Alliah Perico

Luwalhati: Food and Culture Cafe, a culture-focused business, proudly presents delicacies representing the eight rays of the sun from the Philippine Flag. Inspired by the vibrant Paru-Paro festival of Dasmariñas City, the cafe embodies the concept with its butterfly conservatory as a trademark, aiming to leverage the tourism sector of the city. The cafe is currently in the concept stage as the idea started in November 2023. To operate legally, the owners will complete all the legal requirements needed for the cafe. As for the capital, it amounts to 10 million pesos to be sought from investors through an IPO process. Investors will then receive a portion of the profits as dividends. Strategically located in front of Promenade Park, Luwalhati blends traditional and digital marketing approaches to capture a diverse audience ranging from 16 to 24-year-olds. Luwalhati prioritizes affordability and providing high-quality taste for its customers with prices ranging from 12 pesos to 500 pesos. Calculations from the break-even analysis indicate a temporary target of 8 thousand units to sell while having a 50% markup on each product. In its inaugural month, the cafe achieved earnings of 2 million pesos, paving the way for future expansion and innovation.

EXPLORING FILIPINO PARENTAL ACCEPTANCE AND PERSPECTIVES ON COMPREHENSIVE SEX EDUCATION: A STUDY

Proponents: Xyla Mae Brabante, Ariane Nicole Comedia, Jamie Margaret Flores, Orlando Gueta, Deanne Nicole Nati, Jan Marich Porrás

This study examined the attitudes of Filipino parents towards comprehensive sex education (CSE) and its implications for policy and programming in the Philippines. With adolescent sexual health being a significant public health concern, understanding parental attitudes towards CSE in the Filipino context, considering demographic factors such as age, education, and cultural affiliation. Through a mixed-method approach combining surveys and interviews, the study finds that while there is overall support for CSE among parents, variations exist based on demographic characteristics. Younger parents and those with higher education levels tend to display more favorable attitudes, highlighting the importance of tailored approaches in program development. These findings contribute to the growing body of literature on CSE and underscore the need for culturally sensitive interventions that address the diverse needs and values of Filipino families.

Abstracts

ASSESSING THE PERCEPTIONS OF THE DRAWING ARTISTS OF IMUS CAVITE ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ART GENERATORS

Proponents: Raphael Luis Macabantad, Tricia Mae Atip, Maverick Cadalzo, Julie Ann Macey, Nicole Mahinay, Yuji Roldan, Henry Santera, Steven DJ Selda

The sudden proliferation of artificial intelligence art generators has raised significant concerns among artists regarding its impact on the art industry. This study explored artists' perceptions towards AI art generators, addressing both positive and negative viewpoints. Employing a mixed-method approach, the data were collected from Filipino artists within a specific Facebook group. Findings revealed a nuanced perspective, with artists acknowledging the potential of AI as a source of inspiration and efficiency enhancer. However, concerns regarding job security, copyright infringement, and the devaluation of art persist. Thematic analysis of qualitative data and weighted mean analysis of quantitative data elucidate these perceptions. The study underscores the need for continued dialogue among artists, AI developers, and art enthusiasts to navigate the complex interplay between technological innovation and artistic integrity. Researchers recommend fostering open communication, addressing ethical concerns, and exploring long-term effects on the art industry. This research contributes to understanding the multifaceted dynamics surrounding AI art generators and their implications for artistic practice and identity.

SUMI TRAVEL AND TOURS

Proponents: Kyle A. Castañeda, Joshey Ann Isabel O. Jurado, Ruth Faye F. Monte, and Queen G. Villar

SUMI Travel and Tours, founded in October 2023 in Imus City, Cavite, aims to enhance the city's heritage and cultural tourism offerings. With the tagline, "Galing sa Imus, Para sa Imus," it offers enriching travel experiences primarily targeting history enthusiasts. They offer three affordable tour packages showcasing Imus City's rich cultural heritage, involving Cathedral and Heritage Park. Marketing strategies include social media, brochures, and leaflets. Strategic financial research projects a positive outcome, with a net income projection of approximately five million pesos over five years, based on a break-even analysis of 12 packages monthly. The plan emphasizes product diversification, seasonal tour packages and provides a comprehensive guide for the growth and success of its mission and vision for Imus, Cavite's tourism industry.

Proposal Defense: Unlocking Milestones

Aside from the help of the research advisers, the Research Department aims to guide the students in their research progress through a set of panelists in their proposal defense. This activity also helps them to improve their speaking skills and confidence through their presentation.

ENVISIONING A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE, INNOVATION, AND INCLUSION

Senior High School Students conquered a significant milestone in their academic journey as they defended their research during the Proposal Defense.

Grade 12 Students from various strands presented their Business Research, Social Sciences Research, Arts Research, Action Research, TVL Research, and many other discipline-based research proposals. Meanwhile, Grade 11 students presented qualitative research; Junior High School students presented action research.

The Research Department envisions scientific and artistic projects that reflect innovation and sustainability. It dares the student to discover solutions to existing or future problems in the post-pandemic era.

RESEARCH QUIPS

The Gym Leader

The Panel Mystification

The Passing Verdict

Research Defended!

After the data gathering and analyzation of data, the students prepared themselves for their final defense presentation.

ACHIEVING A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE THROUGH RESEARCH

Both Junior High School and Senior High School student researchers accomplished their final defense presentation last April 15-April 29, 2024.

Researchers presented different research such as action research, quantitative research, qualitative research, and mixed-methods research. Moreover, researchers also aimed to achieve the Research Department's Agenda and Sustainable Development Goals through their research.

Furthermore, due to high heat index within the province, most of the groups conducted their final defense via Google Meet.

An English Critic's Journey

A delicate balance needs to be achieved when editing a paper. One must correct grammar mistakes, check for spelling errors, and—of course—ensure that the paper maintains a formal and academic tone. While doing all this, one must also ensure that the paper still sounds human, and not as though it was written by a machine. During my experience as an English critic for senior high school and college students, it was this balance I kept in mind.

Using different tools and years of editing experience at my disposal, I was tasked with editing the research papers of the STEM students. I found the process to be both interesting and rewarding. Most of the papers I worked on had topics I had scarcely heard of before then and the papers with topics I was familiar with explored new and informative angles that I was excited to learn about. A certain paper comes to mind as particularly interesting; titled, “Heat Resilience in Imus Boulevard Road Agricultural Ecosystem: Exploring the Lived Experiences of Old Vegetable Farmers Coping with the High Heat”. The title of this paper alone had me very interested in going through its contents. Reading through it, I found its contents to be wholly interesting, especially since it was very timely. I remember finishing this paper and feeling more informed about the struggles of old vegetable farmers during times of high heat.

Some papers were more challenging than others. Some changed their tone and voice halfway through their sentences. Some had more misspelled words than they had correctly spelled ones. Some ignored the rules of grammar altogether. And most challenging of all, one or two papers that even Grammarly was not able to help make sense of. But there is no reward for those who quit, so I pushed on. In all fairness even with the grammatical mistakes in these papers, the content was still highly informative, and as a lover of knowledge myself, I appreciate the data I was able to gain from them.

With every paper I worked on, I strived to maintain balance. I wanted the writers of these papers to be content with the work I did and to feel a sense of pride in their finished studies. All in all, being an English critic was an outright unique and interesting experience full of learning, challenges, and rewards. An experience that I would gladly go through again.

MS. MARIA LEA JANNEL I. DOMINGO, LPT
English Critic

Presenting Beyond Borders...

One of the aims of the Research Department is to showcase students' research outside the institution.

2ND SOCIETY OF TRANSFORMATIVE EDUCATORS NATIONAL RESEARCH CONGRESS

Rianne Ervie Baniqued
Best Paper Presenter

The Influence of Implementation of the Climate Action Project (CAP) towards Climate Changes as Perceived by Junior High School Students in Unida Christian Colleges

Prince Travis Amado
Paper Presenter

ReCo.ai: Using Generative Pre-trained Transformer 3 Model for a Chatbot in Answering Grade 10 Mathematics Questions

Raphael Luis Macabantad
Paper Presenter

The Perceived Effects of Artificial Intelligence Art Generators on Drawing Artists of Imus, Cavite

2ND CLAE INTER-SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL RESEARCH COMPETITION

Angel Fiona C. Talili, Kazelyn Ballesta, Jennifer Faith Bernardo, Gemmalyn R. Gutierrez, Jonahlei Jhen B. Macabuag, Mark Joshua O. Macahilig, Mavin Russle D. Ordoño
Researchers

Analyzing the Economic Growth Development Through Different Presidential Terms from the 9th President to the 16th President of the Philippines: A Content Analysis

Matt Niño Celada, Jesus Angel A. Alcantara, Catherine B. Celeste, Chenaniah S. Cullados, Aprilyn Dex L. Llana, Jim Christopher A. Persia, Margareth L. Polo, and Kyle Aris Dominguez
Researchers

Perception of Economic Experts on Government's Effort on Mitigating Inflation

Unveiling the Logo

This school year, the institution continues to maintain a cohesive and professional image. To align with the institution's goal, the department utilized a brand new logo which still aims to represent research.

THE MAGNIFYING GLASS

Research, in general, is being represented by the magnifying glass. With the use of this tool, a person can see an object clearly. Likewise, research always aims to magnify or heighten the phenomena, circumstances, and problems that the world is facing today and look for possible solutions.

THE ELEMENTS

The elements present are a light bulb, an atom, a book, and a globe. The light bulb represents the idea; the atom represents the sense of discovery; the book represents knowledge, that must be embodied by the researchers. These elements must align to the world, represented by the globe, and to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals.

THE PEOPLE

The people can represent both the researchers and the community. The researchers, who embodies the elements, conducts research that can explain phenomena and provide recommendations which benefits the community.

THE PLANT

The plant in the logo represents growth. Through conducting research, different aspects of a community improves or grows such as technology, environment, health, economy, social connections, and more.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS: *Our Future, Our Action*

Taking Action Towards a Sustainable Future

Research Department held its 2nd Senior High School Research Colloquium with a theme, "Sustainable Development Goals: Our Future, Our Action," at UCC Audio-Visual Room, May 24, 2024.

Selected research groups from both Grades 11 and 12 presented their research in front of the guest panelists, Ms. Rosa Mae Doloso, Ms. Jezelle Aron-Salvacion, Mr. John Arvin Glo, Mr. David Gayadang, and a resource panelist, Ms. Hanny Pearl Camerino.

After the presentation, selected research groups who got the highest points were recognized with the Best Abstracts, Best Presenters, Best Qualitative Paper, and Best Quantitative Paper. Certificates of participation were also given to all research groups.

2ND SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL RESEARCH COLLOQUIUM

BEST ABSTRACT

Lived Experiences Towards the Translacion Among Selected Black Nazarene Devotees

Qualitative Category

EVOLTREADY: A DIY Electricity Generator Treadmill With Pulley Machinery With the Use of Electric Bike Battery

Quantitative Category

BEST PRESENTERS

Faith Anialyn Mendoza, Ma. Lavinia Manalaysay, Caleb Yeshua Rubio

Qualitative Category

Mark Lester Sabater, Kristina Cassandra Fajardo, Vhyrone Ashley Bala

Qualitative Category

BEST QUALITATIVE PAPER

Strategies in Reusing Leftover Foods Among Selected Micro-Businesses in the Barangay Anabu Area

BEST QUANTITATIVE PAPER

Survey on Perception of Grade 12 Students on Factors That Influence Digital Divide

Publications

RESEARCH DIGEST VOL. 1 NO. 1

Check out the first volume of the Research Digest through scanning the following QR Codes:

Heyzine

Research Gate

MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Check out the recent volume of the Multidisciplinary Research Journal through scanning the QR code:

Zenodo

About the Cover

The United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals aims to end poverty, protect the planet, and ensure that all people enjoy peace and prosperity which is specifically divided into 17 goals. The Research Department supports this objective by implementing the goals when conducting research.

The icons included in the cover, which continues to the back, represents the 17 goals of the United Nations. The theme, "Sustainable Development Goals: Our Future, Our Action," indicates that the humanity's future will be attained through the humanity's action towards the 17 goals.

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- Associate Editor: Rubelyn M. Pagasartonga
- Contributors: Keziah Medilo, Ruby Rose Fundimera, Brian Ian Ben, Maria Lea Jannel Domingo, Joshey Ann Isabel Jurado, Francine Navarro, Jamie Margaret Flores, Raphael Luis Macabantad

**Unida Christian Colleges
Research Department**

